

Progress report from Working Group 4 - *Shared resources and infrastructure to analyze scholarly outputs* - March 2026

1. General information

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Initial Objectives:

- Foster the use of state-of-the-art open source tools for extracting information from full text;
- Encourage the sharing of the extracted metadata within a framework consistent with full-text access licenses;
- Meet the considerable computing and storage requirements via resource pooling mechanisms.

2. Summary of the group's activities since its creation

Number of meetings: 8

Dates of meetings: 16 February 2026

11 December 2025

10 July 2025

9 July 2025

20 May 2025

21 May 2025

Number of participants: 8 – 20 participants per meeting

Key Points of Discussion

- A dedicated session with the French Open Science Monitor to understand its architecture, governance, and operational model.
- Discussion of the Working Group 4 internal survey and review of findings highlighting differences in infrastructure maturity, technical capacity, and institutional mandates.
- Deliberation on the scope and structure of Working Group 4 subgroups, including identification of coordination requirements for subgroups.

Methodologies

- Comparative learning through engagement with national monitoring initiatives such as the French Open Science Monitor.
- An internal survey of Working Group members to gather qualitative and quantitative insights on infrastructure, tools, and monitoring practices.
- Analysis of survey responses to identify patterns in infrastructure readiness, technical approaches, and policy challenges.

Output

- Implementation of a Working Group 4 survey with 22 respondents across 15 countries.
- Development of a blog summarizing survey findings.
- Clarification of subgroup roles and communication structures.

3. Challenges, upcoming activities, deliverables, timeline and working group duration

Challenges

- Low active participation in survey responses from the wider working group.
- Infrequency of meetings
- Limited direction towards joint OSMI goals
- Low active participation on tangible outcomes (code collab, Discord discussions)
- Lack of demographic diversity

Upcoming Activities and Deliverables (Next 12 months)

- Finalization of Working Group 4 subgroups (1–2 months).
- Subgroups to define specific deliverables, scope, and timelines (2–3 months).
- Development of subgroup outputs and synthesis for Working Group reporting (4–12 months).

